

Modeling H₂-enriched dual fuel engine performance and emissions

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ABSTRACT

This study utilizes a validated GT-Power simulation model to evaluate hydrogen (H₂) enrichment effects on the performance and emissions of a four-cylinder, 86 kW dual-fuel diesel engine. The primary goal is identifying operating strategies that enhance efficiency while maintaining nitrogen oxide (NO_x) emissions at or below baseline levels, termed "NO_x neutral" operation. The methodology involves adjusting engine load between 2 and 16 bar brake mean effective pressure (BMEP) and varying H₂ energy substitution from 10% to 70% at 1500 rpm. To analyse complex non-linear relationships, this research employed response surface methodology (RSM) and a random forest (RF) machine learning algorithm. Results indicate optimal H₂ substitution lies in the 20–30% range, yielding a 2–3% improvement in brake thermal efficiency (BTE) and a significant decrease in brake specific fuel consumption (BSFC) from 200–220 g/kWh to 160–180 g/kWh. While CO₂, HC, and CO emissions decreased, NO_x remained stable only up to 25% substitution, increasing sharply thereafter. Consequently, H₂ energy contribution should be limited to 25% to effectively control NO_x. The combined use of simulation with RSM and RF models proves an efficient, accurate method for engine analysis, minimizing extensive physical testing requirements.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The issue of global warming, driven by fossil fuel emissions, is accelerating the search for clean energy alternatives. Hydrogen (H₂) is emerging as a promising carbon-free fuel [1]. Using H₂ in existing internal combustion engines offers a practical way to decarbonize transportation and reduce its carbon footprint [2], [3]. However, employing pure H₂ in engines presents difficulties due to complex combustion processes and increased NO_x emissions [4]. Modifying diesel engines to operate in a dual-fuel setup, where H₂ is the primary fuel and diesel is used for ignition, is a crucial step towards lowering these emissions [5].

The main challenge in converting existing engines to H₂-diesel dual-fuel is controlling NO_x emissions to levels comparable to those of pure diesel, ensuring compliance with regulatory standards. Most in-production engines rely on a traditional mechanical diesel fuel injection system, which has a fixed, single-pulse injection and timing. This inflexibility restricts the ability to optimize injection strategies or integrate additional exhaust gas treatment systems (EGT). Furthermore, operational limits with H₂ are also a constraint, with one

study suggesting that H₂ substitution should be limited to 35% for loads below 50% and 15% for loads above 50% to ensure stable and efficient operation [6]. To optimize dual fuel performance, various control strategies are employed. Injection strategies of both H₂ and diesel are tailored to influence combustion characteristics [7], [8]. Although research on H₂-diesel dual-fuel engines is expanding, a significant gap remains in achieving performance and emission advantages, especially while keeping NO_x emissions neutral. This challenge is particularly relevant for in-production engines, which lack the flexibility of pilot fuel injection and the use of EGT. The majority of published research has focused on single-cylinder engines operating at low loads (brake mean effective pressure (BMEP) under 10 bar) [9], [10]. Consequently, there is a considerable shortage of information on achieving NO_x neutral performance in multi-cylinder, turbocharged in-production engines, particularly at high loads and with increased H₂ energy substitution rates where controlling NO_x poses the greatest challenge [11], [12].

To address this gap, this study utilizes a validated simulation model created with Gamma Technologies (GT-Power). To manage the intricate, non-linear connections between engine parameters and outputs, this research applies two effective techniques: response surface methodology (RSM) for engine optimization [13]-[15], and the random forest (RF) machine learning algorithm for reliable data-driven predictions [16]-[18]. The RF machine learning technique acts as a "virtual engine," allowing for a more efficient exploration of complex trade-offs and precise identification of optimal operating conditions than traditional physical experiments. This study assesses engine performance over a broad spectrum of loads, from 2 to 16 bar BMEP, with H₂ energy substitution ranging from 10% to 70%. The goal is to determine the best operating strategies that enhance efficiency while complying with emission regulations. For this study, H₂ is inducted into the intake system through a port fuel injection (PFI) technique at varying flow rates to ensure a homogeneous air-fuel mixture.

The novelty of this work is a two-fold contribution: A statistical and machine learning methodology was applied to validated simulation data to create a "virtual engine." This approach was extended to a broad range of BMEP for dual-fuel engines, up to 16 bars, and enabled a strategy that increased H₂ substitution without altering the engine's architecture (specifically, the mechanical single-pulse diesel fuel injection system). This work also resulted in a dual-fuel system calibration strategy that maintained the engine-out NO_x level while reducing all carbon-based emissions (CO, CO₂, and HC) and improving thermal efficiency by 2.5%. The subsequent sections of this paper detail the methodology, including the simulation software and sub-models used, the validation process, the application of machine learning, and the results of optimizing H₂ substitution across various BMEP levels.

2. METHOD

In order to derive the maximum H₂ substitution and extend the BMEP range of the engine entirely through experiment is time consuming and involves a lot of cost. Simulation models validated using experimental data are therefore used for engine calibration optimization to reduce the time and money involved in this process. Machine learning techniques are able to create virtual engine models which can be further reused for optimization (increase thermal efficiency and reduce emission).

2.1. Numerical analysis

A one-dimensional engine model was developed in GT-power to replicate the combustion process of a H₂-diesel dual-fuel engine. The simulation employs an advanced calibration procedure that modifies two predictive combustion models: DI-Pulse for the diesel pilot injection and SITurb for the premixed H₂ charge. The simulation schematic layout of the GT-Power model is shown in Figure 1. The calibration process initiates with the cylinder pressure object attribute (CPOA) tool [19], which evaluates experimental in-cylinder pressure data to derive a target net heat release rate (HRR) curve. This curve signifies the total energy released by both fuels. The objective of the calibration is to iteratively adjust the DI-Pulse and SITurb models until their combined HRR output aligns with this target curve. Initially, the parameters of the DI-Pulse model are fine-tuned to correspond with the first sharp peak of the HRR curve, which is indicative of the combustion of the diesel pilot. This model monitors the complete lifecycle of the diesel fuel, from injection to combustion, by segmenting the fuel into various axial and radial zones. It considers droplet breakup, air entrainment, and evaporation, utilizing calibration factors for ignition delay, premixed combustion, and diffusive combustion. Once the DI-Pulse model is calibrated, the SITurb model is modified to align with the subsequent, broader section of the HRR curve, which is primarily influenced by the turbulent combustion of H₂. This model, grounded in the Blizzard and Keck framework, simulates the transition of the flame from a laminar to a turbulent state.

Figure 1. H₂-diesel dual fuel: simulation schematic layout

It computes the rate at which the unburned mixture is drawn into the flame front and the rate at which this mass combusts. The tuning process necessitates an iterative exchange between the two models, as the energy produced from the diesel combustion has a direct impact on the H₂ combustion [20]. This burn rate is computed using the combustion model. Energy equations of unburn and burned zone are mentioned in (1) and (2).

$$\frac{d(m_u e_u)}{dt} = -p \frac{dV_u}{dt} - Q_u - \left(\frac{dm_{f,b}}{dt} h_f + \frac{dm_{a,b}}{dt} h_a \right) + \frac{dm_{f,i}}{dt} h_{f,i} \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{d(m_b e_b)}{dt} = -p \frac{dV_b}{dt} - Q_b - \left(\frac{dm_{f,b}}{dt} h_f + \frac{dm_{a,b}}{dt} h_a \right) \quad (2)$$

Where m_u & m_b represent the masses of the unburned and burned zones, respectively, e_u & e_b denote the energies of the unburned and burned zones, V_u & V_b indicate the volumes of the unburned and burned zones, Q_u & Q_b refer to the heat transfer rates of the unburned and burned zones, p signifies the in-cylinder pressure, t represents time, h_f is the enthalpy of the fuel mass, h_a is the enthalpy of the air mass, $h_{f,i}$ is the enthalpy of the injected fuel mass, $m_{a,b}$ is the mass of air transferred to the burned zone, $m_{f,i}$ is the injected fuel mass, and $m_{f,b}$ is the fuel mass transferred to the burned zone.

2.1.1. “DIPulse” diesel combustion model

The combustion process is governed by key calibration factors such as ignition delay (C_{ign}), premixed combustion and diffusive combustion. The air-entrainment factor (C_{ent}) is calculated according to (3) based on the injector nozzle velocity (u_{inj}) and the subsequent fuel spray breakup time (t_b) to determine the spray tip length (S).

$$\frac{dm}{dt} = -C_{ent} \frac{m_{inj} u_{inj} du}{u^2} \quad (3)$$

$$(S) = \begin{cases} 16 \left(\frac{t}{t_b} \right)^{0.5} & \frac{t}{t_b} \leq 1 \\ 16 & \left(\frac{t}{t_b} \right) \geq 1 \end{cases} \quad (t_b) = 4.351 \sqrt{\frac{2\rho_l}{\rho_g}} \frac{d_n}{C_d u_{inj}} (u_{inj}) = C_d \sqrt{\frac{2\Delta P}{\rho_l}} = \frac{\dot{m}_{inj}}{A_n \rho_l}$$

Where, t is time, S is spray tip length, t_b is breakup time, ρ_g is density of H₂, d_n is diameter of nozzle, C_d is discharge coefficient of nozzle, ρ_l is diesel density, ΔP is nozzle pressure drop, \dot{m}_{inj} is injector out mass flow

rate, A_n is area of nozzle, and u_{inj} is injector nozzle velocity. The ignition delay factor (C_{ign}) is calculated based in (4) based on the ignition delay.

$$(\tau_{ign}) = C_{ign} \rho^{-1.5} \exp\left(\frac{3500}{T}\right) (O_2)^{-0.5} \quad (4)$$

$$\int_{t_0}^{t_{ign}} \frac{1}{\tau_{ign}} dt = 1$$

Where, τ_{ign} is ignition delay, (O_2) is concentration of oxygen within the pulse, T is temperature within the pulse, and ρ is gas density within the pulse. Following ignition, the model calculates the rate of premixed charge mass formation ($\frac{dm_{pm}}{dt}$) and the rate of entrained mass formation for diffusive burning ($\frac{dm}{dt}$) the the premixed combustion factor as mentioned in (5) and diffusive combustion factor as mentioned in (6).

$$\left(\frac{dm_{pm}}{dt}\right) = C_{pm} m_{pm} k (t - t_{ign})^2 f((O_2)) \quad (5)$$

$$\left(\frac{dm}{dt}\right) = C_{df} m \frac{\sqrt{k}}{\sqrt[3]{V_{cyl}}} f((O_2)) \quad (6)$$

Where, t is the current time, t_{ign} is ignition phase duration, m_{pm} is mass of premixed charge, k is premixed stage turbulent flow energy/entrainment stage turbulent kinetic energy, V_{cyl} is entrainment stage cylinder volume, and (O_2) is entrainment stage oxygen concentration. The model accounts for the transition from a spray-dominated combustion to an established flame front. This is achieved by calculating an effective flame area (A_f) as shown in (7).

$$(A_f) = \left(1 - \frac{R_f}{S}\right) A_{spray} + \left(\frac{R_f}{S}\right) A_{flame} \quad (7)$$

Where, A_f is the effective flame area, R_f is the flame front radius or reaction zone thickness, S is the spray tip length, A_{spray} is area of the fuel spray, and A_{flame} is the characteristic area of the flame.

2.1.2. "SITurb" - H₂ combustion model

The characteristic burning time (τ_b) is determined by the laminar flame speed (u_L) as per in (8) and the turbulent burning velocity (u_T) is calculated to describe the flame propagation as per (9). The model calculates the rate at which the unburned mixture is entrained into the flame front and the rate at which this mass burns. Rate of mass entrainment calculated as per in (10) into the flame front ($\frac{dM_e}{dt}$) and then determines the final rate of burned mass formation ($\frac{dM_b}{dt}$) as per in (11) based on the entrained mass (M_e) and the burning time (τ_b).

$$(\tau_b) = \frac{\lambda}{u_L} \quad (8)$$

$$(u_T) = C_{TFS} u' \left(1 - \frac{1}{1 + C_{FKG} \left(\frac{R_f}{L}\right)^2}\right) \quad (9)$$

$$\left(\frac{dM_e}{dt}\right) = \rho_u A_{FF} u_{te} \quad (10)$$

$$\left(\frac{dM_b}{dt}\right) = \frac{M_e - M_b}{\tau_b} \quad (11)$$

Where, τ_b is the burning time, λ is characteristic length scale, u_L is laminar flame speed, u' is turbulent fluctuating velocity, C_{TFS} is turbulent flame speed multiplier, C_{FKG} is flame kernel growth multiplier, R_f is flame radius, L is integral length scale of turbulence, M_e is entrained mass, ρ_u is entrainment stage unburned mixture density, A_{FF} is area of flame front at entrainment stage, u_{te} is entrainment stage turbulent velocity, M_e is entrained mass, M_b is burned mass, and τ_b is burning time.

2.1.3. Apparent heat release rate (AHRR)

Net HRR calculated as per (12) as a function of crank angle [21]. This curve represents the combined energy release from both the diesel and H₂ combustion phases.

$$AHRR = \left(-p \frac{dV}{dt} - \frac{dQ}{dt} - \frac{d(me_s)}{dt} + \sum_i \dot{m}_i h_{i,s} \right) \quad (12)$$

Where $p \frac{dV}{dt}$ is the rate of work done by the system, $-\frac{dQ}{dt}$ is the rate of heat transfer out of the system, $-\frac{d(me_s)}{dt}$ is the rate of change of sensible energy of the mass within the system, $-\sum_i \dot{m}_i h_{i,s}$ is the sum of the enthalpy flows associated with the sensible energy of mass crossing the system boundary, \dot{m}_i is the mass flow rate of species 'i', and $h_{i,s}$ is the specific sensible enthalpy of species 'i'.

2.2. Experimental setup for validating combustion model

For the experimental study, a four-cylinder diesel engine was modified to operate on a dual-fuel mixture of H₂-diesel. Table 1 and Figure 2 depict the engine specifications and the schematic layout of the experimental setup. H₂ was introduced into the intake port through injectors after its pressure was reduced from 250 bar to a level of 2 bar. Diesel acted as the pilot fuel, igniting under compression to initiate the combustion of the H₂-air mixture. Experiments were carried out at four distinct engine loads (4, 8, 12, and 16 bar BMEP), with measurements taken for pure diesel operation as a baseline, followed by tests with H₂ contributing 25% of the total energy input. The H₂ injection was optimized to occur during the intake stroke to ensure a homogeneous mixture and to prevent gas from escaping.

Table 1. Engine specification

Parameter	Unit	Value
Engine make	---	KOEL – 4 cylinders
Bore x stroke	mm	105 x 125
Displacement	Ltr	4.32
Rating	kW	86 kW @ 1500 rpm
Firing order	---	1-3-4-2
Compression ratio	---	15.5 :1
Pilot fuel	---	Diesel
Pilot fuel timing	° BTDC	15° ± 1

The duration of H₂ injection varied from 15.0 °CA to 74.9 °CA for flow rates ranging from 0.5 kg/hr to 2.5 kg/hr. The optimal injection timing was determined to be 45° after gas exchange TDC, which aligns with previous research [22], [23]. Detailed instrumentation list presented in Table 2. Each experiment was repeated three times to ensure reliability, and an uncertainty analysis was conducted to evaluate the overall accuracy, similar to a previous study [24]. The results of the experimental uncertainty are presented in Table 3, while the equipment uncertainty is shown in Table 4. Essential instrumentation, such as pressure and temperature, along with safety measures, such as non-return valves, flame traps, and flame arrestors, have been integrated into the H₂ supply line as shown in Table 2.

Figure 2. H₂-diesel dual fuel: experimental schematic layout

Table 2. Instrumentation

System	Description	Make	Range	Accuracy
H ₂ Gas flow	First stage pressure regulator	GCE	10-250 bar	±1.0% of FS
	2 nd stage pressure regulator	VANAZ	10-250 bar	±1.0% of FS
	H ₂ line Pressure gauge	GCE	0-3 bar, 0-15 bar	±1.0% of FS
	H ₂ Leak detecting sensors	AMBETRONIC	0-100% H ₂	±1.0% of FS
	H ₂ - Flow meter	Aalborg	0-10 kg /hr.	±1.0% of FS
Diesel flow	Gas flash back arrestor	DEMAX	0-5.0 bar, 0-15 bar,	±1.0% of FS
	Diesel flow meter	AVL 735	0-100 cc	±1.0% of FS
Air flow	Venturi flow meter	Eureka	0-800 m3/hr.	±1.0% of FS
Pressure	Pressure sensors	DRUCK	0-5 bar	±1.0% of FS
Temperature	Temperature sensors	Hi-Tech	RTD and Thermocouple	± 0.8 °C up to 200 °C
Emission	Emission analyser	HORIBA MEXA 584L	NO: 0-5000 ppm	1 ppm
			HC: 0-10000 ppm	>2000 ppm, 1 ppm
			CO ₂ : 0-20%	0.1% vol
In-cylinder pressure	Combustion system	AVL INDICOM	720 °CA	±0.5 °CA
	6045 A piezoelectric sensor	Kistler	0 ... 250 bar	20 pC/bar

Table 3. Emission parameters uncertainty analysis

Pollutant	Average reading	% Random uncertainty	% Instrument uncertainty	Total measurement uncertainty (%)
HC (PPM)	85	4.71%	1.70%	2.17%
NO _x (PPM)	634	4.25%	1.70%	1.99%
CO (PPM)	99.3	0%	1.70%	1.70%
CO ₂ (%)	8.1	3.02%	1.70%	1.88%

Table 4. Performance parameters uncertainty analysis

Parameter	Unit	Uncertainty
Voltage	V	±2
Current	A	±1
Diesel mass flow	kg/s	±5.4 × 10 ⁻⁵
H ₂ mass flow	kg/s	±3.3 × 10 ⁻⁶
Total fuel consumption	kg/s	±5.4 × 10 ⁻⁵

2.3. Model validation

A detailed validation of computational models for both diesel and dual-fuel engines was performed by comparing simulation results with experimental data for 4, 8, 12, and 16 bar BMEP with 25% H₂ energy substitution. The graphical depiction of in-cylinder pressure, heat release rate (HRR), and combustion phases at 12 bar BMEP for both diesel and dual fuel modes is illustrated in Figures 3(a) and 3(b), Figures 4(a) and 4(b) for enhanced comprehension. The result shows a strong correlation between simulated and experimental in-cylinder pressure, HRR and combustion phases for both "DI pulse" and combine "DIpulse + SITurb" dual fuel model. The validation confirmed that both models are highly accurate, with an absolute error for in-cylinder pressure within ±5% and a combustion phase prediction error within ±2 °CA. This robustly validated dual-fuel model was then used to simulate a wider range of operating conditions. The consistency in matching curve shapes and peak values across all tested BMEP levels confirms the models' reliability.

Figure 3. Model validation comparing simulation and experimental results for diesel mode at 12 bar BMEP, showing (a) in-cylinder data and (b) combustion phase details

Figure 4. Model validation comparing simulation and experimental results for dual fuel mode at 12 bar BMEP, showing (a) in-cylinder data and (b) combustion phase details

2.4. Response surface methodology (RSM) statistical analysis

To optimize engine performance and emissions, a response surface methodology (RSM) was utilized with a Box-Behnken experimental design [9], [13], [14] as per DoE mentioned in Table 5. The study analyzed influence of three independent factor such as engine load (BMEP), lower calorific value of fuel (LCV) and H₂ energy substitution on response factors like BTE and BSFC, as well as on the emissions including NO_x, HC, CO, and CO₂. Using ANOVA, a quadratic polynomial equation was developed and validated with statistical metrics like R², Adj-R², and Pred-R². The model's strong fit, with an R² value over 80%, confirmed its accuracy for predicting engine behavior and identifying optimal operating conditions.

2.5. Random forest machine learning

This research utilized RF algorithm to predict the performance of a dual-fuel engine [16], [25]. Figure 5 shows the model was built using orange data mining (v3.3) and trained on a normalized dataset of 90 unique data points, which were split into a 70% training set (60 points) and a 30% testing set (30 points). The RF model was designed to predict seven key outputs which are BTE, BSFC, NO_x, HC, CO, and CO₂. The inputs used to make these predictions BMEP, LCV, and H₂ substitution. The core of the model is ensemble learning and bagging, which involves building a "forest" of multiple decision trees.

Each tree was trained on a different random subset of the training data created through bootstrap sampling. To further enhance diversity and prevent overfitting, the current model used the random subspace method, which considers only a random subset of 2 features at each split within a tree. Table 6 shows the hyperparameters for the model were set as follows: 70 trees (n_estimators), maximum tree depth of 7 (max_depth), and a minimum of 3 samples per split (min_samples_split). The model's performance was evaluated using 10-fold cross-validation and a variety of metrics. Key metrics included mean squared error (MSE), root mean squared error (RMSE), and the coefficient of determination (R²) [26], [27]. A successful model was defined as having an R² value of 0.9 or greater, indicating a strong fit with minimal difference between the training and testing results. To combat overfitting, the study leveraged the RF model's inherent randomness in both data sampling and feature selection. Additionally, hyperparameter tuning was performed by adjusting the max_depth, min_samples_leaf, and n_estimators to ensure the model wasn't overly complex and could generalize well to new data.

Figure 5. Orange data mining layout: random forest

Table 5. RSM model - DOE

	BMEP (bar)	LCV (kJ/kg)	H ₂ %	Response
Level 01	2	43500	0	BTE (%)
Level 02	4	46462	10	BSFC
Level 03	6	49857	20	(g/kw.hr)
Level 04	8	53787	30	NO _x (ppm)
Level 05	10	58389	40	CO (ppm)
Level 06	12	63853	50	HC (ppm)
Level 07	14	70445	60	CO ₂ (ppm)
Level 08	16	78555	70	

Table 6. Hyper parameters

Parameters	Selected
Criterion	gini
n_estimators	70
max_depth	7
min_samples_split	3
min_sample_leaf	1
max_features	sqrt

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Brake thermal efficiency (BTE, %)

The contour plot in Figure 6 demonstrates the connection between BTE (%), the percentage of H₂ (H₂-%), used as substitution fuel and BMEP (bar). Increasing H₂ substitution up to 40% boosts BTE by about 1% for every 10% of H₂ added. The highest BTE is achieved when both engine load (BMEP) and H₂ substitution are high. A peak efficiency of 41% was recorded at 40% H₂ and 14 bar BMEP, a 3% improvement over pure diesel. Furthermore, a 2.5% BTE increase is possible without raising NO_x emissions. The observed results are similar to the previous research [28], [29]. Beyond 40% H₂ substitution BTE starts declines from 41% to 38% similar to previous published results [30]. The anticipated reasons for decrease in BTE is mainly due to combination of factors, including combustion phasing, reduced volumetric efficiency, and increased heat loss. H₂ displaces a portion of the incoming air for the same volume and decreases the total mass of the charge [31]. This reduction in the mass of the charge also further support along to a lower BTE [32].

Regression in (13) is a quadratic model of RSM that predicts BTE (%) based on three independent variables: BMEP (bar), the percentage of H₂ substitution (H₂-%), LCV (kJ/Kg). Table 7 provides the model's performance of both RSM and RF. Figure 7 depicts the cross-validation process used to evaluate the model by training and testing it on various subsets of the data multiple times. RF model provides highly accurate and consistent predictions, making it a much more suitable and trustworthy model than RSM model.

$$\begin{aligned}
 BTE (\%) = & 24.7 + 1.36 BMEP + 0.112 H_2 - \% + 0.00004 CV - 0.0078 BMEP * \\
 & BMEP - 0.00037 H_2 - \% * H_2 - \% + 0.000000 CV * CV + 0.0129 BMEP * H_2 - \% - \\
 & 0.000019 BMEP * CV - 0.000004 H_2 - \% * CV
 \end{aligned}
 \quad (13)$$

Figure 7. Cross-validation: random forest-BTE (%)

Table 7. Model accuracy -BTE, %

Metric	RSM model	RF model
R ² (train)	0.9391	0.998
R ² (test/predicted)	0.7703	0.979
Cross-validation R ²	-	0.984

3.2. Brake specific fuel consumption (BSFC, g/kW.hr)

Figure 8 shows the contour plot on the relationship between BSFC, BMEP, and the percentage of H₂ (H₂-%). An increase in H₂ substitution reduces BSFC of approximately 10 g/kW.hr for every 10% of H₂ energy substitution. Specifically, a substitution rate of 40% H₂ results in a decrease in BSFC by 80 g/kW when compared to pure diesel. However, in order to maintain the same NO_x emissions as pure diesel, the improvement in BSFC is limited to 40 g/kW.hr, which represents an 18% reduction relative to pure diesel for a 25% H₂ substitution. The noted reduction in BSFC with H₂ substitution directly reflects the enhanced thermal efficiency of the engine. The improved combustion characteristics facilitate a more efficient conversion of fuel energy into power, thereby requiring less fuel for each kilowatt-hour of energy produced. The results obtained are consistent with findings from previous studies [10], [33].

Regression (14) is a quadratic model of RSM that predicts BSFC (g/kW.hr) based on three independent variables: BMEP (bar), the percentage of H₂ substitution (H₂-%), and LCV (kJ/Kg). Table 8 provides the model's performance of both RSM and RF. Figure 9 depicts the cross-validation process used to evaluate the model by training and testing it on various subsets of the data multiple times. Both RSM and RF model provides highly accurate and consistent predictions, making it a much more suitable with exceptional predictive capability on unseen test data.

$$BSFC(g/kW.hr) = 286 - 4.06 BMEP - 1.52 H_2 - \% - 0.00086 CV + 0.0380 BMEP * BMEP + 0.0115 H_2\% * H_2\% + 0.000000 CV * CV - 0.0096 BMEP * H_2 - \% + 0.000022 BMEP * CV - 0.000007 H_2\% * CV \quad (14)$$

Figure 8. Change in BSFC (g/kW.hr) with respect to H₂ substitution (%) and BMEP (bar)

Figure 9. Cross-validation: random forest – BSFC (g/kW.hr)

Table 8. Model accuracy-BSFC, g/kW.hr

Metric	RSM model	RF model
R ² (train)	0.99	0.99
R ² (test/predicted)	0.98	0.99
Cross-validation R ²	-	0.94

3.3. Nitrogen oxide (NO_x, PPM)

The contour plot illustrated in Figure 10 depicts the correlation between NO_x (PPM), the percentage of H₂ substitution (H₂-%) and BMEP (bar). This research utilized a compression ratio of 15:1, and it was found that with a combination of low CR and H₂ substitution at or below 25%, NO_x emissions remain relatively stable, irrespective of the BMEP. A similar finding was reported in a prior study, which indicated that the addition of H₂ had a negligible impact on NO_x emissions at 20% and 40% [34]. Another investigation also noted a minor reduction in NO_x emissions with small quantities of H₂ addition [35]. However, when H₂ substitution exceeds the 25% threshold, there is a significant increase in NO_x emissions. This rise is particularly notable for all the BMEP levels, where NO_x emissions surge by approximately 200 ppm. This incremental rise in NO_x is attributed to the fact that the combustion of H₂ can occur across a broad spectrum of air-fuel ratios,

and the combustion of a rich air-H₂ mixture at elevated temperatures fosters an optimal environment for the formation of NO_x emissions [36]. Although a 30-40% H₂ substitution was found to be optimal for other performance and emission factors, it led to higher NO_x emissions. Therefore, a 25% H₂ substitution is recommended as a practical compromise. This level provides most of the benefits of higher substitution rates while keeping NO_x emissions low, aligning with the goal of maintaining NO_x levels similar to conventional diesel engines. NO_x emission primarily driven by combustion phasing and oxygen availability. By controlling these parameters, NO_x levels can be kept comparable to conventional diesel engines [37].

Regression (15) is a quadratic model of RSM that predicts NO_x (PPM) based on three independent variables: BMEP (bar), the percentage of H₂ substitution (H₂%), and LCV (kJ/Kg). Table 9 provides the model's performance of both RSM and RF. Figure 11 depicts the cross-validation process used to evaluate the model by training and testing it on various subsets of the data multiple times. Both RSM and RF model provides highly accurate and consistent predictions, making it a much more suitable with exceptional predictive capability on unseen test data.

$$\begin{aligned} NO_x \text{ (ppm)} = & 2704 - 180.0 \text{ BMEP} + 34.9 \% - 0.0278 \text{ CV} + 9.81 \text{ BMEP} * \\ & \text{BMEP} + 0.697 \text{ H}_2\% * \text{H}_2\% + 0.000000 \text{ CV} * \text{CV} - 0.938 \text{ BMEP} * \\ & \text{H}_2\% - 0.00096 \text{ BMEP} * \text{CV} - 0.000521 \text{ H}_2\% * \text{CV} \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

Figure 10. Change in NO_x (PPM) with respect to H₂ substitution (%) and BMEP (bar)

Figure 11. Cross validation: random forest – NO_x (PPM)

Table 9. Model accuracy - NO_x, PPM

Metric	RSM model	RF model
R ² (train)	0.98	0.98
R ² (test/predicted)	0.94	0.98
Cross-validation R ²	-	0.92

3.4. Hydrocarbon (HC, PPM)

The contour plot presented Figure 12 shows the relationship between HC (PPM), the percentage of H₂ substitution (H₂%) and BMEP (bar). HC emissions remain unchanged when H₂ substitution is at or below 10%, irrespective of the brake mean effective pressure (BMEP). Once the H₂ substitution surpasses the 10% threshold, a gradual reduction in HC emissions commences. For each 1% rise in H₂ substitution beyond 10%, HC emissions diminish by 10 ppm. This decrease becomes even more significant when H₂ substitution goes beyond 20%. To achieve NO_x-neutral operation, a 20% reduction in HC emissions is the maximum benefit observed, which occurs at a 25% H₂ substitution rate. Adding H₂ to fuel reduces unburnt HC emissions by making combustion complete and more efficient. This happened because of higher combustion temperatures helped to burn up residual hydrocarbon fuel left over from the initial combustion phase. Faster flame speed ensured the fuel-air mixture is consumed rapidly and thoroughly, leaving less unburnt fuel to escape into the exhaust. Enhanced oxidation hydroxyl radicals (OH) molecules actively break down and oxidize stubborn hydrocarbon molecules, ensuring they are fully burned. Wider Flammability Range of H₂ burn in a wider range of air-to-fuel ratios than diesel. This allows it to burn in pockets of the cylinder where the mixture might be too lean or too rich for diesel to combust on its own, thereby reducing pockets of unburnt fuel. A similar observation was made by a researcher who found that with an 18% H₂ mass share in a compression-ignition (CI) engine running in dual-fuel mode, HC emissions were considerably lower compared to a pure diesel mass share. Specifically, at full load, HC emissions dropped from 130 ppm to 70 ppm, and at 20% load, they

decreased from 40 ppm to 20 ppm [34]. Another study also reported comparable results, indicating a substantial reduction in HC emissions to approximately 1 g/kWh [36].

Regression (16) is a quadratic model of RSM that predicts HC (PPM) based on three independent variables: BMEP (bar), the percentage of H₂ substitution (H₂-%), LCV (kJ/Kg). Table 10 provides the model's performance of both RSM and RF. Figure 13 depicts the cross-validation process used to evaluate the model by training and testing it on various subsets of the data multiple times. Both RSM and RF model provides highly accurate and consistent predictions, making it a much more suitable with exceptional predictive capability on unseen test data.

$$\begin{aligned} HC (ppm) = & 112 - 1.81 BMEP + 2.19 H_2\% - 0.00403 CV - 0.416 BMEP * \\ & BMEP + 0.0192 H_2\% * H_2\% + 0.000000 CV * CV + 0.0217 BMEP * \\ & H_2\% + 0.000121 BMEP * CV - 0.000088 H_2\% * CV \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

Figure 12. Change in HC (PPM) with respect to H₂ substitution (%) and BMEP (bar)

Figure 13. Cross-validation: random forest HC (PPM)

Table 10. Model accuracy -HC, PPM

Metric	RSM model	RF model
R ² (train)	0.98	0.99
R ² (test/predicted)	0.95	0.98
Cross-validation R ²	-	0.93

3.5. Carbon di-oxide (CO₂, %)

The contour plot presented in Figure 14 shows the relationship between CO₂ (%), the percentage of H₂ substitution (H₂-%) and BMEP (bar). In this research, carbon dioxide (CO₂, %) emissions progressively decline as the percentage of H₂ substitution rises. This pattern initiates at 5% H₂ substitution, with CO₂ decreasing by 1% for every 10% increase in H₂ up to 30%. After this threshold, additional H₂ substitution does not influence CO₂ levels.

The optimal range for H₂ substitution is identified as being between 25% and 35%, resulting in an average CO₂ reduction of 3%. These results are consistent with earlier studies, which indicated a significant decrease in CO₂ emissions—from 920 g/kWh to approximately 240 g/kWh—when a 7.5% H₂ volume share was utilized in comparison to pure diesel [38]. The CO₂ emission trends observed in this research also reflect the trends in CO emissions, where reductions in both gases are associated with a decrease in the consumption of carbon-based fuels [39]. A linear correlation was noted between the increase in H₂ energy share and the reduction in CO₂ emissions. The current research findings are comparable to previous studies where a 40% H₂ energy substitution led to a 40% decrease in CO₂ [37].

$$\begin{aligned} CO_2 (\%) = & 23.5 - 0.161 BMEP + 0.301 H_2\% - 0.000726 CV + 0.00509 BMEP * \\ & BMEP + 0.00373 H_2\% * H_2\% + 0.000000 CV * CV - 0.00182 BMEP * \\ & H_2\% + 0.000004 BMEP * CV - 0.000009 H_2\% * CV \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

Regression (17) is a quadratic model of RSM that predicts CO₂ (%) based on three independent variables: BMEP (bar), the percentage of H₂ substitution (H₂-%), LCV (kJ/Kg). Table 11 provides the model's performance of both RSM and RF. Figure 15 depicts the cross-validation process used to evaluate the model by training and testing it on various subsets of the data multiple times. Both RSM and RF model provides highly accurate and consistent predictions, making it a much more suitable with exceptional predictive capability on unseen test data.

Figure 14. Change in CO₂ (%) with respect to H₂ substitution (%) and BMEP (bar)

Figure 15. Cross-validation: random forest CO₂ (%)

Table 11. Model accuracy - CO₂ (%)

Metric	RSM model	RF model
R ² (train)	0.99	0.99
R ² (test/predicted)	0.95	0.99
Cross-validation R ²	-	0.98

3.6. Carbon monoxide (CO, PPM)

The contour plot presented in Figure 16 shows the relationship between CO (PPM), the percentage of H₂ substitution (H₂-%) and BMEP (bar). Increasing the H₂ substitution rate in a dual-fuel diesel engine can significantly reduce CO emissions. Up to a 20% H₂ substitution rate, CO emissions remain unchanged. However, once the substitution exceeds this threshold, emissions begin to drop sharply. For every 10% increase in H₂ substitution, CO emissions decrease by about 50 ppm across all engine loads. The most effective range for reducing CO is between 40% and 50% H₂ substitution, which can lead to a total reduction of 200–250 ppm. To achieve NO_x-neutral operation, a 50–60 ppm reduction in CO emissions is the maximum benefit observed, which occurs at a 25% H₂ substitution rate. This is because H₂ promotes more complete combustion by increasing temperatures and producing hydroxyl (OH) radicals that convert CO to CO₂. Additionally, hydrogen's faster flame speed and ability to burn in leaner mixtures prevent the initial formation of CO. These results are consistent with earlier studies. For example, at 100% load, CO emissions decreased from 3.14 g/kWh in standard diesel mode to 2.31 g/kWh with a 10.1% H₂ energy share in dual-fuel mode [39]. Another study reported nearly zero CO emissions with approximately 28% H₂ mass share in a CI engine at 20%, 40%, and 60% loads [34].

Regression (18) is a quadratic model of RSM that predicts CO (PPM) based on three independent variables: BMEP (bar), the percentage of H₂ substitution (H₂-%), LCV (kJ/Kg). Table 12 provides the model's performance of both RSM and RF. Figure 17 depicts the cross-validation process used to evaluate the model by training and testing it on various subsets of the data multiple times. Both RSM and RF model provides highly accurate and consistent predictions, making it a much more suitable with exceptional predictive capability on unseen test data.

$$\begin{aligned}
 CO \text{ (ppm)} = & 419 - 12.5 \text{ BMEP} - 6.84 \text{ H2\%} - 0.0017 \text{ CV} + 0.335 \text{ BMEP} * \\
 & \text{BMEP} + 0.0436 \text{ H2\%} * \text{H2\%} + 0.000000 \text{ CV} * \text{CV} + 0.221 \text{ BMEP} * \\
 & \text{H2\%} - 0.000151 \text{ BMEP} * \text{CV} - 0.000008 \text{ H2\%} * \text{CV}
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{18}$$

Figure 16. Change in CO (PPM)with respect to H₂ substitution (%) and BMEP (bar)

Figure 17. Cross-validation: random forest CO (PPM)

Table 12. Model accuracy-CO (PPM)

Metric	RSM model	RF model
R ² (train)	0.99	0.99
R ² (test/predicted)	0.97	0.99
Cross-validation R ²	-	0.98

3.7. Result comparison

Tables 13 and 14 present a comprehensive overview of the consolidated results. Table 13 compares the current findings with those of previous studies. While Table 14 specifically focuses on comparing the machine learning predictions with earlier research.

Table 13. Comparison of current research result with previous researches

Author	Engine configuration			Optimal H ₂ substitution %	% of change							
	No cylinder	Speed rpm	BMEP bar		BTE %	BSFC g/kW.hr	NO _x PPM	HC PPM	CO PPM	CO ₂ %	Soot g/kW.hr	
[40]	4	2250	8	7.5%	5.0%	1.2%	17.0%	28.0%	20.0%	8.2%	X	
		1750	9	7.5%	2.0%	5.5%	22.0%	22.0%	16.0%	9.3%	X	
		1250	10	7.5%	2.5%	9.5%	26.0%	31.0%	20.0%	9.3%	X	
[41]	4	1500	11	20.0%	4.5%	25.0%	7.5%	11.0%	5.0%	15.0%	2.5%	
		2200	5	17.5%	7.0%	24.0%	47.0%	X	X	X	X	
			8	17.5%	6.0%	18.0%	50.0%	X	X	X	X	
[11]	4	1500	12	17.5%	10.0%	16.0%	28.0%	X	X	X	X	
		1000	14	17.5%	15.0%	1.0%	61.0%	X	X	X	X	
			6	80.0%	3.0%	22.0%	90.0%	20.0%	80.0%	60.0%	95.0%	
[42]	4	1500	6	80.0%	3.0%	22.0%	90.0%	20.0%	80.0%	60.0%	95.0%	
[43]	4	1500	13	40.0%	3.0%	X	24.0%	2.0%	4.0%	X	X	
Current	4	1500	16	25.0%	2.0%	18.0%	Neutral	20.0%	40.0%	25.0%	4.0%	

Table 14. Machine learning model prediction results of previous literature vs current research comparison

Reference	Model inputs (features)	Model outputs (targets)	Model prediction
[44]	% of H ₂ , load, speed	CO ₂ , CO, NO _x	Overall R ² = 0.89-0.98
[45]	Fuel injection angles, air-fuel ratio, diesel-to-gas exchange rates, fuel rail pressure	NO _x , CO ₂ , THC, BTE, smoke	Overall R ² =0.965
[27]	Biogas flow rate, methane fraction (MF), torque, intake temperature	BTE, HC, CO, NO _x , smoke, Secondary fuel energy ratio	Overall model R ² =0.997
[46]	Load, brake power (BP), NO _x , CO ₂ exhaust gas temperature (EGT)	BTE	Overall R ² =0.99
[47]	NO _x , RPM, HC, fuel composition	CO	Overall R ² =0.89
[48]	Spark advance, fuel-air ratio, engine speed	IMEP	Overall R ² =0.90
[18]	Spark timing, equivalence ratio, engine speed	BTE, combustion phasings	Not specified
Current research	BMEP, H ₂ substitution %, and CV	BTE, BSFC, HC, CO, CO ₂ , NO _x	Overall R ² =0.95-0.99

4. CONCLUSION

Hydrogen as a dual fuel in diesel engines offers a promising approach to improve performance and reduce emissions, though it comes with a trade-off: NO_x emissions. This study used a four-cylinder, 86 kW engine found that increasing H₂ substitution leads to notable gains in engine efficiency and a reduction in most

harmful emissions. The research showed that for every 10% of H₂ added, the BTE increased by about 1%, peaking at 41% with a 40% substitution rate. Beyond this, efficiency declined due to incomplete combustion. Similarly, BSFC decreased by approximately 10 g/kW for every 10% of H₂ added. CO₂, CO, and HC were significantly reduced. CO₂ emissions decreased by 1% for every 10% of H₂ up to a 30% substitution. CO and HC emissions saw sharp reductions once H₂ substitution exceeded 20% and 10%, respectively. However, a critical trade-off was observed with NO_x. Emissions remained stable up to a 25% H₂ substitution rate but increased sharply by about 200 ppm beyond this point. For this reason, the study recommends a 25% substitution as a practical compromise, as it increases BTE by 2.5% while maintaining NO_x levels comparable to a conventional diesel engine.

The study used a validated GT-Power simulation model combined with RSM and a RF machine learning algorithm to efficiently analyse engine performance. The RF model provided the prediction accurate with R² value of 0.98, 0.99, 0.98, 0.98, 0.99 and 0.99 for BTE, BSFC, NO_x, HC, CO₂, and CO respectively, which significantly reduced the need for extensive physical testing. The proposed solution involves a straightforward retrofitting process using a PFI technique for H₂ and a single-pulse, fixed-timing diesel pilot fuel injection system. This allows the existing engine architecture to be retained without complex modifications. This approach enables increased H₂ substitution (up to 25% at 16 bar) while maintaining NO_x levels around 450 ppm, similar to pure diesel. The results meet several regulatory standards, including India's CPCB-II and international IMO Tier II and III.

Future research could explore flexible diesel injection strategies to better control NO_x emissions at higher H₂ substitution rates. It would also be beneficial to investigate the combined use of H₂ enrichment with exhaust gas treatment (EGT) systems to further reduce pollutants. Expanding the engine speed range and developing a multi-objective optimization model could provide a more comprehensive understanding and help find the best balance of performance and emissions.

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS STATEMENT

This journal uses the Contributor Roles Taxonomy (CRediT) to recognize individual author contributions, reduce authorship disputes, and facilitate collaboration.

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C : Conceptualization

M : Methodology

So : Software

Va : Validation

Fo : Formal analysis

I : Investigation

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D : Data Curation

O : Writing - Original Draft

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Fu : Funding acquisition

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

All the authors reports there is no potential conflict of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data can be provided on request.

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